

A Solar Hosting Capacity Analysis on a Synthetic Rural Alaska Microgrid Model

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Executive Summary

The report discusses procedures used to conduct a hosting capacity analysis (HCA) on a synthetic Alaska microgrid model. This includes the test case used, assumptions in the analysis, and the several algorithms implemented. The maximum distribution transformer and line loading observed in the six hosting capacity scenarios are 56.8% and 14.6%, respectively, while the voltage ranged from 0.97 to 0.99 per unit. Results of the HCA indicate that Alaska microgrids may have hosting capacity that exceeds the total feeder load of the tested synthetic microgrid model based on the constraints assessed.

Acronyms

AVEC Alaska Village Electric Cooperative

DERs Distributed Energy Resources

DPV Distributed Photovoltaics

GSU generator step-up

HCA Hosting Capacity Analysis

NDA Non-Disclosure Agreements

PV Photovoltaics

POI Point of Interconnection

PCE Power Cost Equalization

RUS Rural Utilities Services

1PH Single Phase

SP Summer Peak

3PH Three-Phase

WP Winter Peak

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1 Introduction

Alaska is composed of hundreds of microgrids, which are locally controlled electrical grids that may or may not be able to connect to a larger utility grid. Due to Alaska's topography, connection is usually either not economically feasible or not possible, thus most microgrids in the state are permanently isolated. This increases the cost of power in these communities, between three to five times more than in urban areas. According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration, Alaska ranks fifth in order of the highest residential rates in the U.S. at 25.64 cents/kWh.¹ However it is important to note that this number is the state's average, and the cost of electricity is actually higher in remote communities where diesel is the primary source of power generation and fuel must be delivered either by air or boat. As of October 2024, the average rate in areas served by the Alaska Village Electric Cooperative (AVEC) was 22.15 cent/kWh with the Power Cost Equalization (PCE) rate,² a subsidy for rural residents to reduce the energy cost disparities between rural and urban Alaska. Without PCE, electric rates in these communities are about 74 cents/kWh.³ Commercial facilities, including schools, pay the full, unsubsidized rate for electricity. Residents who use more than a monthly cap (currently 750 kWh/month) also pay this full rate for electric usage above the cap.

Renewable energy, especially solar and wind, are local sources of generation that have lower emissions than the diesel most commonly used in rural Alaska and could be a less expensive option. Depending on the size and location of the community, large-scale wind projects may not be economically feasible. However, solar Photovoltaics (PV) is a popular choice as it can be scaled down significantly, from megawatts size to kilowatts, and even can be mounted on roofs. While it is possible for everyone in a community to install rooftop solar and enjoy the benefits of solar energy, it is important to consider the operational limits of the distribution system. The reliability, power quality, and safety of an electric grid is as important as providing affordable and sustainable electricity.

Hosting capacity analysis is performed in this study to better understand the risks associated with high penetrations of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) which includes small-scale wind turbines, electric vehicles, and community solar, in a distribution system. The focus of the analysis outlined in this report is the hosting capacity of Distributed Photovoltaics (DPV) generation.

1.1 What is Hosting Capacity Analysis?

Hosting capacity is the amount of DERs that can be connected to the distribution system before operation limits are reached and upgrades to the distribution system become necessary. Hosting Capacity Analysis (HCA) aims to determine this limit with the fundamental process of iteratively increasing DPV generation until a user-defined constraint is reached. This type of analysis can be complex depending on the complexity of the system, accuracy of analysis, and available data. The three generic quantification methods of HCA, in order of complexity and accuracy, include deterministic, stochastic, and time-series.⁴ The monitored impacts (e.g. loading, harmonics, etc), simulation type,⁵ and the inverter control⁶ can also add complexity to the analysis. Since the test case in this study is a simple radial distribution system, HCA was simplified as discussed in Section 2.

1.2 Test Case

The power system model used in this hosting capacity analysis is a synthetic rural Alaska microgrid model. Synthetic power system models are realistic, but are fictitious and do not represent any real grids. These test cases are

¹U.S. Energy Information Administration. *U.S. Energy Information Administration - EIA - Independent Statistics and Analysis*. URL: <https://www.eia.gov/state/rankings/?sid=AK#series/31> (visited on 11/14/2024).

²Alaska Village Electric Cooperative. *Rates & Understanding Your Bill*. URL: <https://avec.org/customer-service/rates-understanding-your-bill/>.

³Alaska Village Electric Cooperative, *Rates & Understanding Your Bill*.

⁴Enock Mulenga, Math H. J. Bollen, and Nicholas Etherden. "A review of hosting capacity quantification methods for photovoltaics in low-voltage distribution grids". In: *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 115 (Feb. 2020), p. 105445. ISSN: 0142-0615. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2019.105445. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0142061519306490> (visited on 07/21/2024).

⁵Mulenga, Bollen, and Etherden, "A review of hosting capacity quantification methods for photovoltaics in low-voltage distribution grids".

⁶Kelsey A Horowitz et al. *An Overview of Distributed Energy Resource (DER) Interconnection: Current Practices and Emerging Solutions*. en. Technical Report NREL/TP-6A20-72102, 1508510. National Renewable Energy Lab. (NREL), Golden, CO (United States), Apr. 2019, NREL/TP-6A20-72102, 1508510. DOI: 10.2172/1508510. URL: <http://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/1508510/> (visited on 07/21/2024).

developed from statistical data and often leverage machine learning algorithms to construct the synthetic network.⁷ Synthetic models strive to replicate the behavior of the represented grid, from network topology to system behavior, making them great research assets for testing new research ideas without the need for proprietary utility data. This removes the privacy concerns and security risks of using real data, and also removes the need for Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA) between researchers and utilities. The synthetic Alaska microgrid model used in this study is the only available benchmark model that represents an Alaska microgrid and is available to the researchers without an NDA.

⁷Hanyue Li et al. "Building Highly Detailed Synthetic Electric Grid Data Sets for Combined Transmission and Distribution Systems". In: *IEEE Open Access Journal of Power and Energy* 7 (2020). Conference Name: IEEE Open Access Journal of Power and Energy, pp. 478–488. ISSN: 2687-7910. DOI: 10.1109/OAJPE.2020.3029278. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9216129> (visited on 02/08/2025).

2 Methods

A hosting capacity analysis was conducted on a synthetic model of a rural Alaska microgrid to determine the amount of rooftop solar that a rural Alaska community can support before component upgrades are required. The HCA in this study included determining the appropriate tools and methods to conduct the analysis. The following sections elaborate on the parameters and procedures applied in the analysis.

2.1 Test Case: Synthetic Alaska Microgrid Model

Two load scenarios are commonly modeled in a synthetic test case. These two scenarios comprise a load snapshot when summer and winter load are highest: Summer Peak (SP) and Winter Peak (WP), respectively. The performed HCA utilizes the SP load scenario, as rooftop solar output peaks in the summer. It is possible that solar resource peaks outside of summer peak, possibly even coinciding with the summer valley, the time in the summer when load demand is lowest. However, due to lack of data, this load scenario was not modeled in the synthetic grid. The WP scenario was not evaluated in this study as solar irradiance in the winter in Alaska is typically very low and would not result in high output from DPV.

The synthetic model contains five generators and five feeders: two Three-Phase (3PH) and three Single Phase (1PH). From the generation substation, voltage is stepped up from 480 V line to line to 12.47 kV line to line through a generator step-up (GSU) transformer, where the distribution feeders branch off. A simplified diagram of the test model is illustrated in Figure 1. Table 1 summarizes the total load on each feeder and the length of the primary feeder, which is defined as the backbone of the feeder where lateral feeders of the same voltage level branch off to service loads. During SP, the test load scenario, one of the 500 kW and the 250 kW generators are online.

Table 1. Load and length of feeders in the test case.

Feeder	Summer Peak Load (kW)	Primary Feeder Length (miles)
Feeder 1	217.04	3.02
Feeder 2	131.86	0.32
Feeder 3	63.78	0.76
Feeder 4	59.67	0.97
Feeder 5	121.47	1.07
Total	593.81	–

2.2 HCA Tools

DIgSILENT PowerFactory⁸ incorporates various toolboxes for distribution networks, including a Hosting Capacity Analysis tool. The feature virtually inserts a generator at the selected site(s) and incrementally increases the injected power until a user-defined constraint is reached. HCA is performed for individual sites, not simultaneously. For multiple sites, the procedure is done for each site, then repeats to the next site.

PowerFactory 2024 did not support hosting capacity analysis on an AC/BI system type, which represents the split-phase configuration of North American residential systems. This results in the virtual PV systems being connected directly to the feeders. This is not representative of the typical rooftop solar connection to load buses, which are points of connection or nodes where electrical loads are connected to the distribution transformers. Because the synthetic microgrid model used in the analysis employs the dual phase system configuration at the load bus to represent connection to residential systems, the HCA tool was not used for the hosting capacity of rooftop solar. Static generators were manually connected to select load buses for DER connection. Section 2.3 discusses the conditions for rooftop solar hosting sites. Section 2.2.5 discusses the detailed implementation of DPV and the algorithms applied for the analysis.

Although DIgSILENT's Hosting Capacity Analysis function could not be utilized for hosting capacity of DPVs for this test case due to the system type, it was employed to determine the HC of community solar, as described in Section 2.7.

⁸DIgSILENT GmbH. *DIgSILENT PowerFactory*. Gomarigen, Germany, Mar. 2024.

DG 1.135MW_ADG 1.135MW_B DG 0.5MW_A DG 0.5MW_B DG 0.25 MW

Figure 1. Simplified one-line diagram of synthetic Alaska microgrid test case.

2.3 Hosting Site

After determining the method to implement the HCA of rooftop solar, hosting sites and input parameters for the DPV were then selected. Rooftop solar sites were selected based on load and configuration assumptions. The average rooftop solar size in Alaska is 5 kW.

To simplify the selection of DPV hosting sites, the distribution transformer's aggregate load was considered with the assumption that all customers, regardless of load size, install rooftop solar PV. To qualify as a hosting site for DPV, the distribution transformer must have a minimum aggregate load of 5 kW. Table 2 summarizes the total number of

Table 2. Qualified nodes on each feeder and the minimum and maximum load.

Feeder	No. of qualified load bus	Min kW	Max kW
1	18	5.85	35.50
2	9	5.11	62.67
3	5	7.91	14.11
4	6	5.55	9.87
5	11	5.53	12.91

qualified nodes for each feeder and the minimum and maximum load.

2.4 DPV Parameters

The solar PV model’s applicable input parameters are summarized in Table 3. Constant power factor is one of the most common inverter controls and also the default for standards.⁹ Most grid-connected DPVs have a unity power factor (pf=1).¹⁰ In small communities such as rural Alaska where offsetting electric rates are prioritized, it is not economically viable to oversize rooftop solar PV systems as it increases costs. Thus, the DPV model in the study was set to operate at a unity power factor with a constant power factor controller and a maximum power equal to the load to prioritize local power delivery.

Table 3. Parameters utilized to model DPV in PowerFactory.

Generator	Static Generator
Technology	1PH-PH (DPV) 3PH*
Plant Category	Photovoltaic
Parallel Units	1 (default)
Apparent Power (S)	Srated = Pmax = Load
Active Power (P)	Srated = Pmax = Load
Dispatch	P, cos(phi)
Active Power (P)	0.1 kW - Max 0.1 kW incremental increase
Power Factor	1.0
Local Controller	Constant power factor

* PowerFactory HCA tool

2.5 HCA Methods and Algorithms

Hosting capacity analysis is conducted on steady-state conditions, where the network is in a state of equilibrium. For each iteration of increase in PV generation for each algorithm, power flow is conducted and system wide voltage ranges and line and transformer loadings are collected.

2.5.1 HC Algorithms

Two types of algorithms were explored to determine the hosting capacity of the test case: deterministic and streamlined. The deterministic or quantitative methods includes the forward, backward, and all-together approach¹¹ with the fundamental similarity of incrementally increasing the PV at a site until the maximum PV potential is achieved (see Section 2.3) or a user-defined constraint is reached, then moving on to the next node. The differences between the three deterministic methods of increasing PV are:

⁹Horowitz et al., *An Overview of Distributed Energy Resource (DER) Interconnection*.

¹⁰Global Sustainable Energy Solutions. *Power Factor and Grid-Connected Photovoltaics*. 2015. URL: https://www.gses.com.au/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/GSES_powerfactor-110316.pdf.

¹¹Falko Ebe et al. “Evaluation of PV hosting capacity of distribuion grids considering a solar roof potential analysis — Comparison of different algorithms”. In: *2017 IEEE Manchester PowerTech*. June 2017, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/PTC.2017.7981017. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7981017> (visited on 06/04/2024).

- Forward - starts at the beginning of a feeder and continues towards the end
- Backward - starts at the end of a feeder and continues towards the feeder head
- All-together - simultaneously starts at all hosting sites and increases capacity incrementally until max is reached

The streamlined approach is complex, evaluating the impact of DER aggregation in specific locations on power, current, and more.¹² To simplify this method, DERs were placed in certain locations of the system to determine the impact of aggregating rooftop PV in only some parts of the feeder. The locations are at the beginning, middle, and end of feeders. In this analysis, the All-together method was used to add PV in the selected areas and increase PV generation.

2.5.2 HC Case: Feeder

The analysis can be done two ways, 1) each feeder is evaluated independently while the other feeders are placed out of service or 2) all feeders are evaluated at the same time while all feeders are in-service. To represent a more realistic system and capture the impact of DERs and feeder interactions in the system, the latter was utilized. Six hosting capacity feeder cases were conducted for each of the algorithms described in Section 2.5.1 above.

2.6 Analysis Constraints

Hosting capacity analysis typically focuses on four criteria: voltage, component thermal loading, power quality or harmonics, and protection equipment capabilities. This analysis focuses on the voltage and thermal loading criteria of hosting capacity at steady state.

2.6.1 Voltage

Most Alaska systems follow the guidelines of the Rural Utilities Services (RUS). The acceptable voltage range is 0.95 to 1.05 per unit from the RUS Bulletin 1724D-144, which recommends service voltages to be within 5% of the nominal voltage.¹³ For each algorithm and test described in Section 2.5, the voltage and thermal loading throughout the network was scanned and ensured to be within the specified constraint.

2.6.2 Component Loading

Thermal limits of feeder lines and transformers were constrained to 100% loading based on ambient weather conditions.

2.7 Additional Analysis: Community Solar

An additional analysis was conducted in a scenario where communities install a small-scale utility solar PV system, also known as community solar. To expand the energy-saving benefits of solar PV to multiple customers, there is an increasing interest in community solar programs in Alaska.¹⁴ This program allows ratepayers to buy shares of local small-scale solar farms in exchange for receiving a portion of the electrical output of solar farm. Because this type of distributed generation serves larger power demands, they are typically connected to substations or through a three-phase Point of Interconnection (POI) in the grid.

To evaluate the hosting capacity of community solar, PowerFactory's HCA tool was utilized, which was only applicable on 3PH feeders #1 and #2. Twenty-five (25) hosting sites were selected for community solar hosting capacity: 21 from Feeder #1 and 4 from Feeder #2. The hosting sites on the 3PH feeders where PowerFactory connects a virtual static generator for HCA are circled in red in Figures B.1 and B.2 of Appendix B. Results of the analysis for community solar is discussed in Section 3.2.

¹²Matthew Rylander, Jeff Smith, and Wes Sunderman. "Streamlined Method for Determining Distribution System Hosting Capacity". In: *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications* 52.1 (Jan. 2016). Conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications, pp. 105–111. ISSN: 1939-9367. DOI: 10.1109/TIA.2015.2472357. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7219464> (visited on 07/21/2024).

¹³Rural Utilities Service. *BULLETIN 1724D-114: Voltage Regulator Application on Rural Distribution Systems*. Dec. 2017. URL: https://www.rd.usda.gov/files/UEP_Bulletin_1724D-114.pdf.

¹⁴Shivani Bhagat et al. *Scaling Up Community Solar in Alaska*. eng. Tech. rep. Zenodo, Nov. 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14226047. URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/14226047> (visited on 01/25/2025).

3 Results

Hosting capacity analysis of rooftop solar and community solar suggests that the hosting capacity is likely to be greater than the total load in Alaska microgrids based on the constraints assessed, and therefore transmission system or system operation limits would be the limiting factor instead of distribution system limits. This analysis just evaluates the hosting capacity due to distribution system voltage and thermal limits. The hosting capacity being near the total system load, due to distribution system limits, is primarily due to the relatively short feeders and sparse load locations along the feeder. The base case, which is the normal system during SP with no distributed generation, had voltages ranging from 0.96 per unit to 0.99 per unit, which is within the specified voltage limits of 0.95 per unit and 1.05 per unit in normal system conditions. Various algorithms were executed as described in Section 2.5, and even with all feeders having greater than 5 kW of DERs per node, the voltage changed minimally as observed in Table 4 below.

3.1 Rooftop Solar

The algorithms described in Section 2.5 were executed in the hosting capacity analysis of rooftop solar with all PV installations reaching the maximum potential assumed for this study but not maximum hosting capacity in all cases.

Table 4 summarizes the amount of DPV added in each of the hosting capacity scenarios and the resulting voltage range and transformer and line loading. The Scenario ‘Base’ is the system before the addition of DPVs, the ‘Feeder’ cases represent the scenarios when the DPVs in the selected feeder are online and generating at maximum capacity, and the ‘All Feeders’ case is when all the DPVs in all feeders are simultaneously online and generating at maximum output.

In the HCA of rooftop solar, DPV penetration for the test case ranged from 7.09% in Feeder #4 to 86.57% in All Feeders with minimal change in voltage range and a decrease in transformer and line loading. For all HC scenarios, voltage range remained within the Base case range of 0.96 to 0.99 per unit, while the maximum loadings for the distribution transformers and feeder lines were 56.8% from Feeder #5 and 14.6% from Feeder #4, respectively.

Table 4. Total DER added, voltage range, and transformer and line loading of the feeders from hosting capacity analysis.

Scenario	Load (kW)	DER Added (kW)	DPV Penetration (%)	Voltage Range (per unit)	Transformer Loading (%)	Line Loading (%)
Base	593.81	0	0.00	0.96 - 0.99	33.3 - 62.9	0.2 - 14.5
Feeder 1	217.04	207.69	34.98	0.97 - 0.99	17.1 - 33.2	0.3 - 14.5
Feeder 2	131.86	127.93	21.54	0.97 - 0.99	16.3 - 45.8	0.2 - 14.5
Feeder 3	63.78	50.16	8.45	0.98 - 0.99	16.2 - 56.3	0.2 - 14.5
Feeder 4	59.67	42.08	7.09	0.98 - 0.99	16.8 - 41.8	0.2 - 14.6
Feeder 5	121.47	86.20	14.52	0.97 - 0.99	11.2 - 56.8	0.2 - 11.4
All Feeders	–	514.06	86.57	0.97 - 0.99	11.2 - 53.4	0.2 - 6.9

3.2 Community Solar

The results of the analysis, which includes the maximum active power that can be injected into the system before the user-defined constraints (see Section 2.6) are violated, are summarized in Table 5. As tabulated below, individual hosting sites are able to accommodate between 1.80 MW to 2.19 MW, which is approximately 3 times the total summer peak load, before loading or voltage constraints are identified. The limiting components for the majority of the hosting sites is the generator step up transformer (GSU) from thermal overload and Terminal (7) on Feeder #1 from over-voltage. As the GSU is part of the transmission system, not the distribution system, the only limiting factor in the tested synthetic microgrid model is the over-voltage of Terminal (7) located at the end of the 3-mile long primary feeder. The location of the community solar hosting sites are circled in Appendix B.

All of these results only considered distribution system limiting factors. The hosting capacity of DERs in rural Alaska may be more limited by transmission system limiting factors. Additional analysis would need to be performed to assess the actual hosting capacity of DERs in the system, accounting for both distribution and transmission limiting factors.

Table 5. Hosting sites for community solar.

Feeders	Hosting Site	Max. active power (kW)	Max. loading (%)	Max./Min. Voltage (per unit)	Limiting component
FEEDER#1	Terminal(7)	1800	78.006	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(8)	1870	82.369	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(67and6)	1940	86.769	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(11)	2010	91.103	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(12.11)	2010	91.149	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(9)	2020	91.594	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(16)	2030	91.953	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(17)	2040	92.32	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(12)	2060	94.254	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(10)	2130	98.643	1.05	Terminal(7)
FEEDER#1	Terminal(13)	2130	99.425	1.042	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(3)	2170	99.449	1.019	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(4)	2190	99.463	0.978	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(10-14)	2140	99.518	1.047	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(1)	2160	99.53	1.02	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(5)	2110	99.563	1.021	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(2)	2180	99.734	1.019	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(14)	2140	99.739	1.045	GSU
FEEDER#1	F#1_node1	2100	99.889	1.021	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(15)	2150	99.921	1.047	GSU
FEEDER#1	Terminal(68)	2150	99.988	1.047	GSU
FEEDER#2	Terminal(41)	2080	99.934	0.97	GSU
FEEDER#2	Terminal(40)	2080	99.68	0.97	GSU
FEEDER#2	Terminal(25)	2070	99.532	0.97	GSU
FEEDER#2	F#2_node1	2070	99.762	0.97	GSU

4 Conclusions

Hosting capacity analysis is critical in understanding the operational limits of existing distribution systems with increasing distributed energy resource penetrations. As rooftop and community solar penetrations in rural Alaska increase as a means of decreasing the cost of power, it is crucial to understand the operational limits of the distribution system's electrical components. In the hosting capacity analysis of the six scenarios for rooftop solar where PV penetration ranged from 7.09% to 87.57%, the maximum loadings for the distribution transformers and feeder lines were 56.8% and 14.6%, respectively. The minimum and maximum voltage observed were 0.97 and 0.99 per unit, respectively.

The hosting capacity analysis of both distributed PV and community solar PV on a synthetic Alaska microgrid model indicate that Alaska microgrids may have hosting capacity that exceeds the total load per feeder based on the constraints assessed, allowing high DER penetrations without reaching the distribution system's limits.

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Appendix A Hosting Capacity: Rooftop Solar PV

Appendix A contains supplemental diagrams and results associated with the hosting capacity analysis of rooftop solar PV or DPV.

A.1 Feeder Diagrams with DPV

Figure A.1. HCA of Feeder #1 illustrating the PV models on the selected 18 hosting sites.

Figure A.2. HCA of Feeder #2 illustrating the PV models on the selected 9 hosting sites.

Figure A.3. HCA of Feeder #3 illustrating the PV models on the selected 5 hosting sites.

Figure A.4. HCA of Feeder #4 illustrating the PV models on the selected 6 hosting sites.

Figure A.5. HCA of Feeder #5 illustrating the PV models on the selected 11 hosting sites.

Appendix B Hosting Capacity: Community Solar

B.1 Hosting Sites

The list of hosting sites for community solar on the 3PH 12.47 kV feeders are summarized in Table 5 and circled in red in Figures B.1 and B.2 for Feeders #1 and #2, respectively.

Figure B.1. Hosting sites for community solar PV on the 3PH Feeder #1.

Figure B.2. Hosting sites for community solar PV on Feeder #3, which includes a 3PH and 1PH-N section..